

DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5

Version 5

Description

Data Management Plan for "Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections" - version 5

Started from the Open Science Project 2023-24 - Team atreides - UNIBO

Funder

University of Bologna

Grant

Open Science Course
(<https://www.unibo.it/it/studiare/dottorati-master-specializzazioni-e-altra-formazione/insegnamenti/insegnamento/2023/443753>)

Researchers

Erica Andreose (orcid:0009-0003-7124-9639), Leonardo Zilli (orcid:0009-0007-4127-4875), Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772)

Organizations

University of Bologna, Italy

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP - Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections - Open Science Project - version 5

Description:

Data Management Plan for "Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections" - version 5

Started from the Open Science Project 2023-24 - Team atreides - UNIBO

Researchers:

Erica Andreose (orcid:0009-0003-7124-9639)

Leonardo Zilli (orcid:0009-0007-4127-4875)

Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772)

Organizations:

University of Bologna, Italy

Contact: Zilli Leonardo (leonardo.zilli@studio.unibo.it), Andreose Erica (erica.andreose@studio.unibo.it), Di Marzo Salvatore (salvatore.dimarzo2@studio.unibo.it)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: University of Bologna

Grants: Open Science Course (<https://www.unibo.it/it/studiare/dottorati-master-specializzazioni-e-altra-formazione/insegnamenti/insegnamento/2023/443753>)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Iris in Index - Version 3

This dataset contains the bibliographic records from the May 30 2025 data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) infrastructure of the University of Bologna (UNIBO) (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that are found within the OpenCitations Index data dump dated July 2025 (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651), either as citing or cited entity.

-DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v3>

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This dataset contains the bibliographic records from the May 30 2025 data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) infrastructure of the University of Bologna (UNIBO) (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that are found within the OpenCitations Index data dump dated July 2025 (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651), either as citing or cited entity.

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v3>

1.1.5 What is its format?

.parquet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

182 kb zipped

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that is present in OpenCitations Index (15 July 2025 - 10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v6).

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset consists of the research output available in Iris, the implementation of the Current Research Information System, that is present inside of OpenCitations Index as citing and cited entities.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

This dataset provides useful information regarding the number of citations of the entities of UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that are present in OpenCitations Index (15 July 2025 - 10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v6).

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v3>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCAT, DC Terms, FOAF

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>

b. <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

c. <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

scientometrics, informetrics, bibliographic metadata, OpenCitations, open research information, academic publishing

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

figshare

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879441.v3>

Figshare is an online digital repository designed to store, share, and manage research outputs. It is widely used by researchers, institutions, and publishers to make their research data more accessible and citable.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

ISO27001

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Iris in Index

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Python, pandas library

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

This dataset can be read with a virtual environment to open the .parquet files.

Follow the software readme here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

Follow the software protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will be used to verify the content of UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) present in OpenCitations Index (15 July 2025 - 10.6084/m9.figshare.24356626.v6).

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Yes it provides references to the entities present in OpenCitations Meta.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Data Manager

b. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

Data Manager

c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

Data Manager

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Iris no ID - Version 3

The "IRIS No ID" dataset contains bibliographic records from the May 30, 2025 data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) at the University of Bologna (UNIBO). Specifically, it includes only those records without any persistent identifier (PID), such as DOI, PMID, or ISBN.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v3>

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This is the dataset generated after running the software (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>) to retrieve all of the entities in UNIBO Iris dump (30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that do not have an identifier.

<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v3>

1.1.5 What is its format?

.parquet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

9kb zipped

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in UNIBO Iris dump (30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that does not have an identifier.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset consists of the research output available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427), the implementation of the Current Research Information System, that does not have an identifier.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

This dataset provides useful information regarding the entities in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that do not have an identifier.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

a. Yes

Investigating Bibliographic Entities Without Persistent Identifiers. - Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025

b. Yes

Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's publication metadata in an existing source of open research information

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v3>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCTA, DC Terms, FAOF

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>

b. <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

c. <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

scientometrics, informetrics, bibliographic metadata, OpenCitations, open research information, academic publishing

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

figshare

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897759.v3>

Figshare is an online digital repository designed to store, share, and manage research outputs. It is widely used by researchers, institutions, and publishers to make their research data more accessible and citable.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

ISO27001

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Iris no ID

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Python, pandas library

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

This dataset can be read with a virtual environment to open the .parquet files.

Follow the software readme here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

Follow the software protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The data will be available for download on Figshare.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata links to the software readme file:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

And software protocol: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT, DC Terms, FOAF

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The described dataset provides references to the UNIBO Iris bibliographic dump of May 30 2025 (updated July 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427).

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files

- Data cleaning

- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Data Collection

b. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

Data Manager

c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

Data Manager

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump - version 4

This update dataset (30-05-2025) contains several CSV files detailing the bibliographic data of all the publications by UNIBO scholars as stored in IRIS, which is the national platform for storing bibliographic data.

In "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_MASTER_ALL.csv" was added the type column.

In particular, the dataset is made of eight distinct files:

- "README.txt": this document
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_CON_PERSON.csv": information about the people involved in the publications (authors, editors, etc.)
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_DESCRIPTION.csv": the string of the authors and other related metadata of publications
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_IDENTIFIER.csv": the identifiers (including DOIs) of publications
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_LANGUAGE.csv": the language in which the publication has been written (when applicable)
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_MASTER_ALL.csv": basic metadata information of publications (title and date of publication)
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_PUBLISHER.csv": the publishers of publications

- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_RELATION.csv": additional metadata related to the context of publications (publication venue, editors, etc.)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

We have used the Iris bibliographic data dump dated 30 May 2025, updated on 3 July 2025 (deposited 09 Lug 2025 08:45) to analyse the research output of the University of Bologna.

(30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427)

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This dataset contains several CSV files detailing the bibliographic data of all the publications by UNIBO scholars as stored in IRIS (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427), which is the national platform for storing bibliographic data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

All the data provided in the .csv files have been made available in CSV format, using ',' (comma) as field delimiter and '"' (double quotes) for text delimiter (when necessary).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

126 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product

The Data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in the dataset within OpenCitations Meta.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

"The data set consists of the bibliographic metadata of the publications (of various kinds) of the scholars at the University of Bologna. These information has been extracted from the data available in the IRIS platform of the University (<https://cris.unibo.it/>), that implements the Current Research Information System."

(30 May 2025 - DOI: 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

The dataset provides useful insights related to the scientific output of the research conducted within the University of Bologna and related metadata.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

a. Yes

Exploring the Coverage of the Scientific Production of the University of Bologna within OpenCitations

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7608

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

AMS Acta

AMS Acta is the institutional open access repository which enables the researchers of the Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna to share, preserve and showcase their scientific works making them easily accessible, citable and reusable. The repository collects and disseminates unpublished research such as preprints, technical reports, working papers, conference proceedings, research data and software. Moreover, it collects series and books published by the University Departments and Research teams.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Other

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump, dated 30 May 2025, updated on 3 July 2025

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data analysis.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

There are references among the provenance dataset and the OpenCitations Meta.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification

- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Data Manager

b. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

Data Manager

c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

Data Manager

d. Alberto AMURRI (0000-0002-9879-777X)

Co-creator

e. ELENA GIACHINO (0000-0001-8884-044X)

Co-creator

f. Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Ennio Misuraca

Co-creator

g. Silvio Peroni (orcid: [0000-0003-0530-4305](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0530-4305))

Co-creator

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The dataset is archived on the university AMSActa repository, with a unique DOI (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427).

It has also been archived by us on figshare to create a single endpoint of the data available to the user for the reproducibility of the experiment.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's bibliographic and citation metadata in OpenCitations collections

-Open Science Project Software -Team Atreides - version 4.0.0

Software suite for the Open Science project - version 4.0.0

Template: Horizon Europe

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

We haven't considered reusing any kind of software because we wanted to develop something ad hoc for this project.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The software used will be a python script to analyse the data from OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651) and Iris dump (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427).

1.1.5 What is its format?

.py, JSON, CSV, XML, .parquet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

11 mb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

We will answer these research questions:

1) What is the coverage of the publications available in IRIS, that strictly concern research conducted within the University of Bologna, in OpenCitations Meta?

2) What is the types of publications that are better covered in OpenCitations Meta?

3) What is the amount of citations (according to OpenCitations Index) the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations Meta are involved in (as citing entity and as cited entity)?

4) How many of these citations come from and go to publications not included in IRIS, and how many of these citations involves publications in IRIS as both citing and cited entities?

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

The software used will provide users with a view on the extension of the IRIS publications and the ones that cite IRIS inside of OpenCitations Meta.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Exploring the Coverage of the Scientific Production of the University of Bologna within OpenCitations

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

Yes

UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump, dated 30 May 2025, updated on 3 July 2025

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers

DOI

ORCID

Software "open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code: v4.0.0" DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Dublin Core

Metadata regarding the creators and the description of the software are available in the software repository in the "metadata.ttl" file.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Metadata regarding the creators and the description of the software are available in the software repository in the "metadata.ttl" file.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

Dublin core

DCAT

Foaf

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

b. <https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat.rdf>

c. <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. GitHub

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

b. Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Software for query and analysis of OpenCitations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The software will be available on the Github Repository of the Open Science Course of the University of Bologna 2023-2024:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main?tab=readme-ov-file>

The software is stored on SoftwareHeritage:

https://archive.softwareheritage.org/browse/origin/?origin_url=https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code

The GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

The software is stored on Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

The software present a protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Further specifications about the output datasets are provided in the dataset descriptions present in this DMP.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The software will be available on GitHub, SoftwareArchive and Zenodo.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Other

ISC License

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Dublin Core

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

ISC License

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

Readme files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

None

Euro

Other

Data Analysis and Software Development

There will be no real cost in making the Software since it is all based on Open software and data that is publicly available

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

b. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Main creator

c. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The software will be available on the Github Repository:

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

The software is available at this DOI linked to Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Iris Not in Meta - Version 3

The "IRIS Not in Meta" dataset contains bibliographic records from the May 30, 2025 data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) at the University of Bologna (UNIBO) (30 May 2025 - DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that are not found in the OpenCitations Meta data dump dated June 2025 (10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

The dataset is composed of 1 .parquet file.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v3>

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This is the dataset generated after running the software (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>) to retrieve all of the entities of UNIBO Iris (DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) not present in OpenCitations Meta (10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v3>

1.1.5 What is its format?

.parquet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

634 kB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that is not present in OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset consists of the research output available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427), the implementation of the Current Research

Information System, that is not present in OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

The dataset will be useful to researchers that want to explore how many entities inside of UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) are not present in OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's publication metadata in an existing source of open research information

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v3>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

- DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)
- Dublin Core

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCAT, DC Terms, FOAF

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

- a. <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
- b. <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
- c. <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

scientometrics, informetrics, bibliographic metadata, OpenCitations, open research information,

academic publishing

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

figshare

<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v3>

Figshare is an online digital repository designed to store, share, and manage research outputs. It is widely used by researchers, institutions, and publishers to make their research data more accessible and citable.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.3 Add certification(s)

ISO27001

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25897708.v3>

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Iris Not in Meta

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be available for download on figshare.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Python, pandas library

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

A virtual environment is needed to read the parquet file inside of the dataset.

Follow the software readme here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

Follow the software protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The data will be available for download on Figshare.

Follow the software readme here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

Follow the software protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT, DC Terms, FOAF

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The described dataset provides references to UNIBO the Iris bibliographic dump of May 2025 (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427).

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

Open Science course

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Data Collection

b. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

Data Manager

c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

Data Manager

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Iris in Meta - Version 3

This dataset contains the bibliographic records from the May 30 2025 data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) infrastructure of the University of Bologna (UNIBO) (30 May 2025 -DOI 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) that are found within the OpenCitations Meta data dump dated June 2025 (9 June 2025 - 10.5281/zenodo.15625651).

-DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

This dataset contains the bibliographic records from the May 30 2025 (10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427) data dump of the Current Research Information System (CRIS) infrastructure of the University of Bologna (UNIBO) that are found within the OpenCitations Meta data dump dated June 2025.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This is the dataset generated after running the software (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>) to retrieve all of the IRIS entities present in OpenCitations Meta.

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

1.1.5 What is its format?

.parquet

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

8 kb zipped

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

The data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - [10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427](https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427)) that are present in OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - [10.5281/zenodo.15625651](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15625651)).

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset consists of the research output available in UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - DOI [10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427](https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427)), the implementation of the Current Research Information System, that are present in OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - [10.5281/zenodo.15625651](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15625651)).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

This dataset will be useful to the researchers that want to explore coverage of UNIBO Iris (30 May 2025 - [10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427](https://doi.org/10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427)) inside of OpenCitations Meta (9 June 2025 - [10.5281/zenodo.15625651](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15625651)).

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

Analysing the coverage of the University of Bologna's publication metadata in an existing source of open research information

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

An xml/rdf file with metadata is provided with the .parquet file at the download link: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCAT, DC Terms, FOAF

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

a. <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>

b. <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

c. <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

scientometrics, informetrics, bibliographic metadata, OpenCitations, open research information, academic publishing

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

figshare

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

Figshare is an online digital repository designed to store, share, and manage research outputs. It is widely used by researchers, institutions, and publishers to make their research data more accessible and citable.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25879420.v3>

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Iris in Meta

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The data will be available for download on figshare.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Python, pandas library

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

A virtual environment is needed to read the parquet files inside of the dataset.

Follow the software readme here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16759255>

Follow the software protocol:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.g6xmbzfk7>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The data will be available for download on Figshare.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The described dataset provides references to the Iris bibliographic dump of 30 May 2025 - 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/8427.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

UNIBO

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid: [0009-0007-4127-4875](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4127-4875))

Data manager

b. Erica Andreose (orcid: [0009-0003-7124-9639](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7124-9639))

Data manager

c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid: [0009-0006-0853-1772](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-0853-1772))

Data manager

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

None

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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